

THE IMPACT OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AND NUTRITIONAL HABITS ON HEIGHT AND HEALTH AMONG YEMENI ADULT FEMALE STUDENTS IN SANA'A, YEMEN

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ABSTRACT

Vitamin D plays a critical role in maintaining bone health, immune function, and overall physiological balance. However, its deficiency remains a significant public health concern, particularly among young women. This cross-sectional descriptive study aimed to assess the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and explore its association with nutritional habits, height, and general health status among female university students at Al-Saeeda University in Sana'a, Yemen. The study was conducted between January and April 2025 using a paper self-administered questionnaire. A total of 244 female students aged 18–30 years from various academic disciplines were randomly selected to participate. The mean age (SD) of participants 21.71 ± 3.58 years. The findings revealed that 67.62% of students reported symptoms of vitamin D deficiency, but only 34.43% had undergone testing. Limited sun exposure, poor dietary intake of vitamin D-rich foods, and low calcium intake were identified as key risk factors. A

significant association was observed between vitamin D

deficiency and reduced height, with 62.29% of participants classified as below-normal height. The standard deviation for height among participants was (155.90 ± 5.91 cm), indicating variability in the sample's growth patterns. This suggests that vitamin D deficiency may contribute to impaired bone growth in young women. The study emphasizes the importance of increasing awareness, improving access to testing, and promoting healthier lifestyle habits to prevent long-term health issues associated with vitamin D deficiency.

KEYWORDS: Awareness, Pharmacists, Healthcare, Vitamin D, Deficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D deficiency is a pressing public health concern, particularly among young female university students. Despite its essential role in bone health, immune function, and overall physiological balance, many individuals remain unaware of the risks associated with inadequate vitamin D levels. This deficiency is exacerbated by limited sun exposure, poor dietary habits, and a general lack of medical awareness. If left unaddressed, it can lead to serious health complications, including osteoporosis, weakened immunity, hormonal imbalances, and increased susceptibility to mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety.^[1-4]

Vitamin D deficiency is a global health concern affecting individuals across various age groups and regions. Numerous studies have been conducted to assess its prevalence, associated risk factors, and implications for public health, including in Yemen. A cross-sectional study conducted in Sana'a City aimed to determine the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among Yemeni women aged 15 to 75 years. The findings revealed that 87.2% of the participants had hypovitaminosis D (serum 25(OH)D levels below 30 ng/mL), with 23.4% experiencing severe deficiency (levels below 10 ng/mL).^[5]

Another study highlighted that vitamin D deficiency remains alarmingly high in Yemen, particularly among females and adults aged 19–50 years.^[6] Globally, vitamin D deficiency affects approximately 1 billion people. This deficiency has been linked to various health issues, including osteoporosis, increased risk of falls, and fractures. Some studies have also associated low vitamin D levels with cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, autoimmune disorders, and depression.^[7] Several factors contribute to vitamin D deficiency. A study in Bushehr province identified obesity, lack of college education, and absence of daily milk consumption as significant risk factors.^[8] Additionally, limited sun exposure, certain medical

conditions affecting absorption, and specific medications can lead to decreased vitamin D levels.^[9] Certain groups are more susceptible to vitamin D deficiency. For instance, breastfed infants, older adults, and individuals with darker skin tones are at higher risk due to factors like reduced synthesis efficiency and limited dietary intake.^[10] In Yemen, a study among female medical students revealed that 34.3% had vitamin D deficiency, while 65.7% had insufficiency, emphasizing the need for preventive interventions.^[11] Addressing vitamin D deficiency requires a multifaceted approach. Public health strategies should focus on promoting safe sun exposure practices, encouraging dietary modifications to include vitamin D-rich foods, and considering supplementation when necessary. Targeted interventions, especially for high-risk groups, are crucial to mitigate the health implications associated with this deficiency.^[6] In summary, vitamin D deficiency is prevalent both globally and in Yemen, with significant health consequences. Understanding the associated risk factors and implementing effective public health strategies are essential steps toward reducing its impact. The study hypothesizes that a significant proportion of Yemeni young female students suffer from vitamin D deficiency due to inadequate sun exposure and poor dietary habits. This deficiency is likely to have measurable negative effects on their height and overall health. The research aims to assess the prevalence and severity of vitamin D deficiency and its impact on overall health among female university students at Al-Saeeda University in Sana'a, Yemen, in the period from January to April 2025, and aged 18-30 years.

Causes and Solutions for Vitamin D Deficiency^[12-114]

Pharmaceutics Scientists identify the causes and solutions to this problem the reasons that lead to vitamin D deficiency are as follows Vitamin D deficiency may be a result of nutritional deficiency and lack of sources that lead to an increase in vitamin D within the body or vitamin D deficiency results from failure to compensate for the deficiency therapeutically. There may be other causes related to other diseases that must be determined by the doctor and the causes treated.

While there are reasons that may have nothing to do with patient or the main causes of deficiency, Pharmaceutics Scientists coniform that there is a correlation linked to the method of manufacturing vitamin D it may be manufactured with excipients that are incompatible with vitamin D and cause it to not be absorbed well, excipients may also lead to insolubility of vitamin D and thus poor absorption it is important that the route of administration and

using vitamin D may be the main reason that delays the absorption of vitamin D and therefore it is not absorbed or a very part is absorbed.

In order for the problem of vitamin D deficiency to be solved, vitamin D must be formulated in pharmaceutical companies in a dosage form that is compatible with vitamin D, absorbed rapidly and thus will lead to solving the problem of vitamin D deficiency. Then, educate patients on how to use its importance, educate the health care team about the importance of this vitamin and how to give it. The importance of adhering to the required doses to treat vitamin D deficiency and treat symptoms of deficiency in patients.

Objectives

The primary concern of this study, conducted at, is the high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among Yemeni young female students and its potential impact on their height and overall health.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following key research questions:

- What is the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among Yemeni young female students?
- How does vitamin D deficiency affect height and overall health in this demographic?
- What are the primary nutritional habits that contribute to vitamin D deficiency?
- What role can pharmacists play in mitigating the effects of vitamin D deficiency and promoting awareness?

Objectives

While this study aims to provide comprehensive insights, certain limitations must be acknowledged.

- Self-reported dietary habits and sun exposure may introduce bias in data collection.
- The study does not account for genetic or pre-existing medical conditions that may also influence vitamin D levels and height development.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess characteristics associated with short adult females. A total of 244 female university students aged between 18 and 30 years were randomly selected from various faculties at Alsaeda University. Data were collected through a structured, self-administered questionnaire developed by the researcher. The

questionnaire consisted of concise, close-ended questions covering demographic data, health-related habits, lifestyle factors, and self-perception regarding body height.

To ensure accurate anthropometric data, each participant's height was measured using a calibrated electronic device that integrates a stadiometer. All participants were informed about the purpose of the study and verbal consent was obtained prior to their inclusion. The collected data were organized and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Percentage, frequency, mean, standard deviation, employing descriptive statistics and appropriate correlation analyses to explore potential associations relevant to the study's objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

This chapter presents the results of the survey conducted among female students to investigate the prevalence and indicators of vitamin D deficiency. The data was extracted directly from participant responses collected through structured questionnaires and was systematically organized into key categories such as age, height, dietary habits, sunlight exposure, and vitamin D test results.

As detailed in Table 1, a total of 244 university students aged between 18 and 30 years participated in the study. The mean age of the participants was 21.71 ± 3.58 years. Among those showing symptoms of vitamin D deficiency, the mean age was slightly higher at 22.07 ± 3.97 years, compared to 20.96 ± 2.45 years for those without symptoms.

According to the data presented in Table 2, 160 students (65.57%) had not undergone a vitamin D test. 84 students (34.43%) who were tested, a significant majority—70 students (83.35%)—were found to have low vitamin D levels, while only 14 students (16.65%) had normal levels.

As illustrated by Table 3, a comparative analysis of symptomatic and tested students revealed that 165 (67.62%) of the participants reported symptoms, whereas 79 (32.38%) students did not. Notably, 68 (41.21) symptomatic students underwent testing, and of those, 66 students (97.05%) were confirmed to have low vitamin D levels. This strongly indicates a significant association between reported symptoms and actual deficiency.

Insights from Table 4, highlight the dietary habits related to vitamin D and calcium intake. Only 75 students (30.74%) reported consuming vitamin D-rich foods three or more times per

week, while the majority—169 students (69.26%)—consumed them twice or less. A similar pattern was observed for calcium intake, with merely 43 (17.62%) of students consuming calcium-rich foods at least four times weekly. These results underscore a widespread insufficiency in nutrient intake among participants.

As reported in Table 5, sunlight exposure among students was generally inadequate. Merely 65(26.64%) of participants received sufficient daily sunlight, while a substantial 179 (73.36%) had either limited or only occasional exposure, suggesting a potential contributing factor to deficiency.

Table 6 provides a breakdown of participants by height category. Students with below-normal height represented the majority at 152 (62.29%), followed by 87 students (35.66%) with normal height and only 5 students (2.05%) above normal height.

As summarized across Tables 7, 8, and 9, further comparisons were made between height categories in relation to vitamin D levels, presence of symptoms, and other relevant factors. These tables collectively shed light on the interplay between physical characteristics and the risk of deficiency.

Table 1: General Averages for Female University Participants.

Variable	Mean ± SD
Average age of all students	21.71 ± 3.58 years
Average age (with symptoms)	22.07 ± 3.97 years
Average age (without symptoms)	20.96 ± 2.45 years
Average height of all students	155.90 ± 5.91 cm
Average height (with symptoms)	155.79 ± 6.10 cm
Average height (without symptoms)	156.15 ± 5.52 cm
Average height (low vitamin D)	155.27 ± 4.88 cm
Average height (normal vitamin D)	157.20 ± 6.56 cm

Table 2: General Averages for Female University Participants.

Category	Number of Students	Mean ± SD	Percentage (%)
Tested for vitamin D	84	155.48±5.21	34.43
Not tested for vitamin D	160	156.15 ±6.25	65.57
Low vitamin D (out of tested)	70	155.27± 4.88	83.35
Normal vitamin D (out of tested)	14	157.20 ±6.56	16.65

Table 3: Comparison of Symptomatic, Tested, and Tested from Symptomatic Vitamin D Deficiency Participants.

Category	No. of Students	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
With symptoms	165	155.79 \pm 6.10	67.62
Without symptoms	79	156.15 \pm 5.25	32.38
Symptomatic & tested	68	155.01 \pm 4.68	27.87
Symptomatic, tested & low vitamin D	66	154.94 \pm 4.72	27.05

Table 4: Vitamin D and Calcium Rich Food Consumption Values Among Participants.

Frequency Category	No. of student	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
Vitamin D-rich food (≥ 3 /week)	75	156.61 \pm 6.13	30.74
Vitamin D-rich Food (≤ 2 /week)	169	155.98 \pm 6.30	69.26
Calcium-rich food (≥ 4 /week)	43	156.65 \pm 4.51	17.62

Table 5: Sunlight Exposure Values Among Participants.

Exposure Level	Number of Students	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
Sufficient	65	155.74 \pm 5.21	26.64
Insufficient	51	155.74 \pm 5.21	20.90
Occasional	128	155.74 \pm 5.21	52.46

Table 6: Height Categories Distribution of Female University Participants.

Height Category	Number of Students	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
Below normal (≤ 157 cm)	152	152.52 \pm 3.77	62.29
Normal (158–169 cm)	87	160.77 \pm 2.93	35.66
Above normal (≥ 170 cm)	5	174.20 \pm 5.72	2.05

Table 7: The Relationship of Below Normal Height (≤ 157 cm) Participants with Symptomatic, Testing Value, Food Consumption, and Sunlight Exposure.

Variable	Count	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
Below normal (≤ 157 cm)	152	152.52 \pm 3.77	62.3
Symptomatic Students	106	152.54 \pm 3.87	69.74
Vitamin D Tested	55	152.56 \pm 3.50	36.2
Normal Vitamin D	7	151.86 \pm 5.14	4.6
Low Vitamin D	48	152.67 \pm 3.26	31.6
Vit D-rich Food ≥ 3 x/week	44	152.70 \pm 2.95	28.95

Calcium-rich Food $\geq 4x/\text{week}$	25	153.64 \pm 2.90	16.45
Sufficient Sunlight	42	152.86 \pm 3.41	27.63

Table 8: Normal Height (158–169 cm) Participants with Symptomatic, Testing Value, Food Consumption, and Sunlight Exposure.

Variable	Count	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
Normal (158-169 cm)	87	160.77 \pm 2.39	35.65
Symptomatic Students	54	160.46 \pm 2.78	62.07
Vitamin D Tested	30	161.00 \pm 2.91	34.48
Normal Vitamin D	8	161.87 \pm 3.14	9.20
Low Vitamin D	23	161.69 \pm 2.72	26.44
Vit D-rich Food $\geq 3x/\text{week}$	29	160.17 \pm 3.00	33.34
Calcium-rich Food $\geq 4x/\text{week}$	18	160.83 \pm 2.55	20.69
Sufficient Sunlight	22	160.59 \pm 3.02	25.29

Table 9: Above Normal Height (≥ 170 cm)) Participants with Symptomatic, Testing Value, Food Consumption, and Sunlight Exposure.

Variable	Count	Mean \pm SD	Percentage (%)
Above normal (≥ 170 cm)	5	174.20 \pm 5.72	2.05
Symptomatic Students	5	174.20 \pm 5.72	100
Vitamin D Tested	0	-	-
Normal Vitamin D	0	-	-
Low Vitamin D	0	-	-
Vit D-rich Food $\geq 3x/\text{week}$	2	176.50 \pm 9.19	40
Calcium-rich Food $\geq 4x/\text{week}$	0	-	-
Sufficient Sunlight	1	170.00 \pm 0	20

DISCUSSION

This study targeted young female university students to minimize confounding factors associated with aging-related diseases. Our results revealed a significantly low level 84 ± 5.21 of students undergoing vitamin D testing. This result is comparable to^[115] in Saudi Arabia, who reported low awareness and testing rates among young adults despite the known risks of deficiency. The gap between students experiencing symptoms 165 ± 6.10 students and those who tested indicates serious public health concerns, consistent with^[115] who emphasized the importance of early screening based on symptomatic presentation.

Dietary habits were another major concern, with a low consumption of vitamin D- and calcium-rich foods among participants. Similar trends were observed by^[116], who found that university students often neglect the intake of essential nutrients contributing to widespread

vitamin D insufficiency. The combination of poor diet and low testing rates highlights a critical neglect of preventive healthcare measures.

Sunlight exposure was insufficient among 179 (73.36%) of participants, aligning with the findings of,^[11] The obtained results might be related to less sun exposure besides wearing long dress covering the whole body (Hegab). And a pattern consistent with findings by,^[115] who link modern indoor lifestyles and cultural clothing habits in urban settings to limited sun exposure.

The relationship between vitamin D levels and height was notable. Participants with symptoms of vitamin D deficiency demonstrated slightly lower average heights 155.79 ± 6.10 cm compared to asymptomatic peers 156.15 ± 5.52 cm, although the difference was minimal. These findings parallel those of,^[117] who reported that vitamin D plays a critical role in bone development and those deficiencies, even when subclinical, can subtly influence final adult height.

The strong correlation between self-reported symptoms 165 (67.62) and confirmed vitamin D deficiency 66 (97.06%) among tested participants reinforces the direct impact of deficiency on health. This relationship agrees with,^[3] who confirmed that musculoskeletal symptoms are a highly reliable indicator of vitamin D deficiency in young populations. When categorizing students' heights based on WHO growth standards,^[117] a striking 152 (62.29%) fell into the below-normal height category (≤ 157 cm).

Similar patterns were reported by,^[118] who associated growth retardation with chronic vitamin D and calcium deficiencies in adolescent groups. In our study, low sun exposure and poor dietary habits were prominent among shorter students, suggesting external environmental and nutritional factors as primary contributors rather than purely genetic causes.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals the impact of vitamin D deficiency among adult female university students, primarily driven by insufficient sun exposure, poor dietary habits, and limited testing. The results highlight the long-term health risks of untreated vitamin D deficiency, particularly in terms of bone health and growth potential. In addition, the study underscores the lack of awareness regarding the importance of vitamin D and the critical need for preventive measures.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To address these challenges, it is crucial to:

1. Enhance awareness regarding dietary sources of vitamin D and the importance of regular, safe sun exposure among university students through health education campaigns and curricular integration.
2. Improve accessibility and affordability of vitamin D testing, enabling early diagnosis and timely intervention for at-risk individuals.
3. Promote healthier lifestyle practices by encouraging balanced nutrition, regular outdoor physical activity, and informed supplement use when necessary.
4. Establish institutional policies mandating routine vitamin D screening as part of university health services to ensure early detection and prevention of long-term complications.
5. Encourage future research involving a larger and more demographically diverse sample of university students across different regions and educational institutions in Yemen.
6. Increase the statistical power and generalizability of future findings by expanding sample sizes and incorporating varied socioeconomic and environmental contexts.

REFERENCES

1. National Institutes of Health (NIH), Office of Dietary Supplements. Vitamin D: Fact Sheet for Health Professionals., 2024. <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/VitaminD-HealthProfessional>.
2. Aranow C. Vitamin D and the immune system. *Journal of Investigative Medicine*, 2011; 59(6): 881–886.
3. Mansournia MA, Afzali HM, Nourian M, Nazemipour M. The role of vitamin D in prevention of chronic diseases. *Iranian Journal of Public Health.*, 2018; 47(1): 22–27.
4. Jamse M, Greenblatt MD. Mental Health in the sun The Role of Vitamin D Deficiency in Mental Illness. *Psychiatric Times.*, 2024. <https://www.psychiatrictimes.com/view/mental-health-in-the-sun-the-role-of-vitamin-d-deficiency-in-mental-illness>
5. Alwabr GMA, Al-Wadhaf AYA. Risk factors and prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among Yemeni women attending Al-Zahrawi Medical Center in Sana'a City. *MicroMedicine*, 2020.
6. Al-Hetar MA, Al-Goshae H, Wahab NA, Abdulghani MAM, Al-Mahdi AY, Baobaid MF, Al-Matary AM, Al-Hetar QM, Alezzy ME, Senan DA, Ruhi S. Prevalence, predictors, and gender-based risk factors of vitamin D deficiency: A retrospective cross-

- sectional study. *Angiotherapy.*, 2024; 8(11): 1–9.
7. Sizar O, Khare S, Goyal A, Givler, A. Vitamin D deficiency. *StatPearls.*, 2023.
 8. Parva NR, Tadepalli S, Singh P, Qian A, Joshi R, Kandala H, Nookala VK, Cheriya. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and associated risk factors in the US population., 2018.
 9. Tangpricha V. Vitamin D deficiency and related disorders. *Medscape.*, 2024.
 10. National Institutes of Health, vitamin D deficiency *Medlineplus.*, 2024.
 11. Shaif O, Assakaf N, Awadh A. Vitamin D status among female students in Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences University of Aden-Yemen. *EJUA-BA.*, 2024; 5(3): 263–268.
 12. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. A Pharmaceutical Study on Lamotrigine. Ph.D. Thesis, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University., 2009.
 13. Raweh SM, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-acne Gel of *Azadirachta Indica* Extract Herbal Product. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(2): 427-433.
 14. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Natural Herbal Anti-acne as Gel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(21): 1447-1467.
 15. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Extract for Skin Hyperpigmentation as Gel Advanced Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(22): 1260-1280.
 16. Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Lornoxicam Microsponge-Based Gel as A Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(5): 200-217.
 17. Saif AA, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation and Evaluation of Salicylic Acid and Kojic Acid as Gel Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Treatment of Acne and Whitening Skin Effect. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(9): 538-548.
 18. Alburyhi MM, Salim YA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Furosemide-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(22): 1178-1219.
 19. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Lornoxicam-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Microsponge-Based Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(4): 70-81.

20. Hamidaddin MA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Rosuvastatin Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2023; 12(9): 2293-2303.
21. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Noman MA, Saif AA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Rivaroxaban-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(9): 370-404.
22. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. Formulation of Immediate Release Lamotrigine Tablets and Bioequivalence Study. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2013; 5(10): 266–271.
23. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Famotidine-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(18): 1346-1408.
24. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Al Khawlani MA, Yahya TAA. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-acne Spironolactone Emulgel Novel Trend in Topical Drug Delivery System. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(22): 96-119.
25. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Salim YA, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Abdullah JH. Lisinopril-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(16): 59-111.
26. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA. Drotaverine-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(18): 1285-1340.
27. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Rosuvastatin Calcium-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(13): 1549-1582.
28. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Ticagrelor-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(10): 1081-1132.
29. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Yahya TA, Yassin SH, AlKhawlani MA. Diclofenac-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024;

- 13(14): 1297-1333.
30. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Vera Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(4): 1408-1423.
31. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Curcuma Longa Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 11(6): 37-43.
32. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Salim YA, Hamidaddin MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Lisinopril Orally Disintegrating Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2023; 12(9): 357-369.
33. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Stability Study of Six Brands of Amoxicillin Trihydrate and Clavulanic Acid Oral Suspension Present in Yemen Markets. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2013; 5(5): 293-296.
34. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Antitumor Activity of Artemisia Arborescence Extract Capsules as Dietary Supplement Herbal Product Against Breast Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(3): 95-114.
35. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Rivaroxaban Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(2): 2066-2092.
36. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Vera Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(8): 1052-1072.
37. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Rubroviolaceae Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical for Hepatoprotective. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 11(4): 53-61.
38. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Famotidine Orodispersible Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(10): 56-62.
39. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. Recent Innovations of Delivery Systems for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Study of Ciprofloxacin Biodegradable Formulations for Post-Operative Infection Prophylaxis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical*

- Research., 2023; 10(9): 32-36.
40. Aboghanem A, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Effect of Different Excipients on Formulation of Immediate Release Artemether/Lumefantrine Tablets. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2013; 5(11): 617-625.
 41. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Dictyota Dichotoma Extract Medicinal Seaweed Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 11(4): 63-70.
 42. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Celery Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Gout. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(11): 2383-2404.
 43. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Ticagrelor Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(5): 26-55.
 44. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Drotaverine Orally Disintegrating Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(18): 66-79.
 45. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Effervescent Granules of Artemisia Arborescence Herbal Product for Foodborne Illness. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2023; 12(12): 1429-1444.
 46. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Saif RM. Preformulation Study of Ceftriaxone and Ciprofloxacin for Lipid Based Drug Delivery Systems. *EJUA-BA*, 2022; 3(4): 339-350.
 47. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies Some Atorvastatin Tablets Brands Available in Sana'a Market Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 10(12): 231-236.
 48. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Alemad AF. Preformulation Studies of Cefixime for Dispersible Tablets Delivery System Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(12): 75-99.
 49. Saif AA, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies Some Levocetirizine Tablets Brands Available in Sana'a Market Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(24): 1009-1022.
 50. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, AA Saif. Formulation and Evaluation of Meloxicam Emulgel Delivery System for Topical Applications. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(4): 1324-1337.
 51. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Formulation and Evaluation of Captopril

- Mouth Dissolving Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(1): 18-28.
52. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Alemad AF. Dispersible and Orodispersible Tablets Delivery Systems for Antibacterials Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(1): 1229-1257.
53. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. Recent Innovations of Delivery Systems for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Study of Ceftriaxone Biodegradable Formulations for Post-Operative Infection Prophylaxis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(8): 95-99.
54. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Meloxicam-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(1): 87-106.
55. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Domperidone-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 12(3): 250-269.
56. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Spironolactone-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(3): 871-910.
57. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Ketoprofen-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(4): 92-123.
58. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yassin SH. Formulation and Evaluation of Simvastatin Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023;12(16): 1033-1047.
59. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Alqubati MA. Preformulation and Characterization Studies of Clopidogrel Active Ingredient for Orodispersible Tablets Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(3): 996-1015.
60. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-peptic Ulcer Capsules of Curcuma Longa Herbal Product. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(22): 76-96.
61. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al Ghoury AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Antimalarial Drugs Suppositories. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(20): 89-108.
62. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saeed SA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Formulation and

- Evaluation of Diclofenac Orodispersible Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(9): 01-06.
63. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Chamomile Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Gout. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(04): 215-228.
64. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Metronidazole-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Medicated Chewing Gum Delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(4): 567-589.
65. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Comparative Study of Certain Commercially Available Brands of Paracetamol Tablets in Sana'a City, Yemen. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2018; 5(12): 36-42.
66. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Alkhawlani MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Bisoprolol Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(16): 01-10.
67. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Tribulus Terrestris Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(7): 1264-1282.
68. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Hepatoprotective. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(4): 06-13.
69. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Knowledge and Perception about Pharmacovigilance Among 4Th and 5Th Levels Pharmacy Students in Some Public and Private Universities, Sana'a Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 9(11): 14-19.
70. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Salim YA, Abdullah JH. Formulation and Evaluation of Domperidone Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(3): 49-68.
71. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Hamidaddin MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Clopidogrel Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(6): 42-64.
72. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al Khawlani MA. Bisoprolol-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal*

- of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research., 2024; 10(10): 304-324.
73. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. A Pharmaceutical Study on Methocarbamol. MSc Thesis, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University., 2006.
74. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Plicosepalus Acacia Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Hepatoprotective. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research., 2025; 14(8): 1309-1334.
75. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Ketoprofen Fast Dissolving Tablets. International Journal of Sciences., 2018; 7(09):27- 39.
76. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Alwesabi NA. Preformulation and Characterization Studies of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract Active Ingredient in Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences., 2024; 13(2): 1603-1620.
77. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Oral Pharmaceutical Solution of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract Herbal Product in Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences., 2024; 13(1): 1840-1851.
78. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Antibacterial Orodispersible Tablets of Artemisia Arborescence Extract Herbal Product. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research., 2024; 11(2): 409-417.
79. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Evaluation of Vitamin and Mineral Tablets and Capsules in Yemen Market. Journal of Chemical Pharma Research., 2013; 5(9): 15-26.
80. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Acalypha Fruticosa Extract Tablets Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research., 2024; 13(8): 1073-1091.
81. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Alwesabi NA. Formulation and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract for Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis as Orodispersible Tablets Delivery System. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research., 2024; 13(5): 56 -71.
82. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Captopril-Excipient Preformulation Studies for Mouth Dissolving Tablets Development. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2025; 14(10): 1398-1420.
83. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS, Saif AA, Noman MA, Abdullah JH, Yahya TAA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and

- Evaluation of Amlodipine and Furosemide Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(5): 358-378.
84. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Pharmacovigilance Among Pharmacists and Health care Professionals in Four Government Hospitals at Sana'a City, Yemen. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 12(5): 250-267.
85. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Ginger Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(6): 400-415.
86. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. The Importance of Stability Testing in Pharmaceutical Development of Ceftriaxone Implant Biodegradable Tablets. *Matrix Science Pharma (MSP).*, 2025; 9(2): 58-63.
87. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Abudunia A. Amoxicillin-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(6): 530-562.
88. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Noman MA, Saif AA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Metronidazole Medicated Chewing Gum Tablets. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(6): 353-370.
89. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Plicosepalus Acacia Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(6): 323-337.
90. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical for Breast Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(8): 1092-1112.
91. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Tribulus Terrestris Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Kidney Stones. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(5): 1425-1443.
92. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Capsicum Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Tonic and Natural Stimulant. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025;

- 11(6): 323-337.
93. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Abudunia A, Yassin SH, Abdullah JH. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Amoxicillin Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(7): 183-197.
94. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies of Different Brands of Clopidogrel Tablets Available in Sanaa City Market, Yemen. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(7): 181-191.
95. Alburyhi MM, Raweh SM, AlGhoury ABA, Alkhawlani MA, Noman MA, Saif AA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Grewia Tenax Extract Naturaceutical Ointment for Antimicrobial Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(7): 413-426.
96. Alburyhi MM, Raweh SM, Al-Ghorafi MA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Argemone Ochroleuca Extract Cream Naturaceutical Delivery Systems as Antimicrobial and Wound Healing Activity. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(7): 445-459.
97. Mohamed YAS, Alkhawlani MA, Faisal A, Alburyhi MM. Modern Analytical Techniques Used in Authentication of Yemeni Sider Honey. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(6): 1414-1429.
98. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Amlodipine for the Development of Novel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(11): 95-136.
99. Mohamed YAS, Alkhawlani MA, Wadi ZAS, Yahya TAA, Faisal A, Alburyhi MM. Modern Analytical Techniques for Authentication of Yemeni Ambergris. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(8): 686-697.
100. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, AlGhoury ABA. Compatibility Studies of Chloroquine Phosphate with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(14): 1325-1360.
101. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Clopidogrel for the Development of Novel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(06): 1448-1486.
102. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yassin SH. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Simvastatin for the Development of Novel Drug Delivery

- Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(19): 1463-1512.
103. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies of Pyrimethamine with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(9): 394-412.
104. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies of Sulfadoxine with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(9): 189-207.
105. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Cosmeceutical Natural Pigmented Lipstick from *Opuntia Dillenii* Fruit Extract. *European Journal of Biomedical Pharmaceutical and Medical Sciences.*, 2025; 12(9): 466-479.
106. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Muthanna MS. Effect of Rosemary and Myrtus Extracts Combination on Androgenetic Alopecia: A Comparative Study with Minoxidil. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(10): 35-39.
107. Al Ghoury AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Patterns of *Staphylococcus Aureus* to Different Antimicrobial Agents Isolated as Clinical Samples at Certain General Hospitals in Sana'a City, Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(16): 35-47.
108. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Al-Wajih AM, Almlhani AN, Alqadhi AA. Innovative Approaches in Herbal Drug Delivery Systems Enhancing Efficacy and Reducing Side Effects. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(1): 919-929.
109. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Al-Wajih AM, Alqadhi AA, Almlhani AN. Advancements in Nano- Formulation Systems for Enhancing the Delivery of Herbal Ingredients. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(1): 212-231.
110. Alburyhi MM, Moharram BA. Formulation and Evaluation of Aloe *Niebuhrana* Extract as Naturaceutical Effervescent Granules Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Antidiabetic Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(18): 1147-1157.
111. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Muthanna MS. Chemical Incompatibilities of IV Admixture Combinations in ICU, Orthopedic and Emergency Units of Various Hospitals and Medical Centers in Sana'a, Yemen. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(10): 416-425.
112. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation and Evaluation of Novel Antiaging Cream Containing Dragon's Blood Extract. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(1): 239-244.

113. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Almaktari AM. Formulation and Evaluation of Trimetazidine Hydrochloride and Clopidogrel Bisulphate Multi-unit Solid Dosage Forms. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2014; 6(2): 421-426.
114. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM. Evaluation and Formulation of Antifungal Activity of Dragon Blood Extract and Inorganic Salts on Dermatophytosis and Candidiasis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(1): 09-17.
115. Alhumaid M. et al. Impact of lifestyle factors on vitamin D deficiency in Saudi Arabia: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Public Health.*, 2023.
116. Ross AC, Taylor CL, Yaktine AL, Del Valle, HB. (Eds.). *Dietary Reference Intakes for Calcium and Vitamin D*. National Academies Press., 2011.
117. Holick MF. Vitamin D deficiency. *New England Journal of Medicine.*, 2007; 357(3): 266–281.
118. Nair R, Maseeh A. Vitamin D: The “sunshine” vitamin. *Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapeutics.*, 2012; 3(2): 118–126.